

CLEWs Insights on Thailand's Energy Transition

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Executive Summary

Thailand faces significant sustainability challenges as its energy sector remains heavily reliant on fossil fuels, responsible for nearly 70% of the country's greenhouse gas emissions. This study applies the CLEWs (Climate, Land, Energy, and Water systems) framework to explore how Thailand's energy transition affects CO₂ emissions, land use, and water demand. Three scenarios were modeled: business-as-usual (BAU), achieving 51% renewable electricity production by 2037, and a net-zero pathway by 2050.

Results show that under BAU, fossil fuels continue to dominate, while crop demand and cropland steadily decline. Achieving the 51% renewable target reduces energy-sector emissions by 14.6% and requires a 4.5% increase in investment. The net-zero scenario shifts the power mix toward solar, wind, and hydro, resulting in an ~87% reduction in water demand for power generation but requiring 158% higher investment. Policy insights emphasize diversifying the energy mix, phasing out coal, expanding renewable and storage technologies, and refining models with national data to align with Thailand's climate neutrality goals.

1. Introduction

The energy sector is Thailand's largest source of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, contributing approximately 69% of total CO₂-equivalent emissions. To address climate change, Thailand has committed to achieving carbon neutrality by 2050 and net-zero emissions by 2065. In support of these targets, the energy sector has developed strategic plans, including the Power Development Plan (PDP), which targets 51% renewable electricity generation by 2037 while also enhancing energy security. Decarbonizing electricity generation is therefore essential to meeting these commitments and carries significant implications for water demand, land use, and agricultural systems.

The Climate, Land, Energy, and Water systems (CLEWs) framework provides an integrated approach to assess these interconnections, capturing trade-offs and synergies across sectors. Applying CLEWs to Thailand's power sector enables the development of baseline and alternative scenarios to evaluate pathways for reducing CO₂eq emissions. This study aims to explore how decarbonization strategies in electricity generation interact with land and water systems, providing evidence-based insights to guide sustainable, low-carbon development and support long-term policy planning toward Thailand's **net-zero and renewable energy transition targets**.

2. Methodology

This study employs the **Climate, Land, Energy, and Water systems (CLEWs) modeling framework** to analyze interactions between energy production, water resources, and land use in Thailand, with a focus on CO₂eq emission reduction. The CLEWs model is an integrated, dynamic tool that captures sectoral trade-offs and synergies, enabling assessment of decarbonization pathways for the power sector under water and land constraints.

Data sources for this study included information on the energy system, such as electricity generation, technology costs, and future projections, obtained from the International Energy Agency (IEA) and the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) Starter Data Kit for Thailand. The CCG Starter Kit provides historical and projected energy data from 2015 to 2070; for this study, data from 2020 to 2055 were extracted and formatted for input into the model. The period 2020–2023 was used for historical calibration of the model, while 2024 onwards represents the optimization period. In Thailand, electricity generation is primarily supplied by two main types of power plants: renewable energy sources—including solar, wind, biomass, and hydro—and fossil fuel sources, mainly coal and natural gas.

Land use and crop statistics were obtained from FAOSTAT, maintained by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations, to parameterize irrigation requirements and biofuel production potential. In Thailand, the three main crops are rice, natural rubber (in primary form), and sugarcane, which is used for biofuel production. Land in Thailand is classified into several types, including forests, water bodies, built-up areas, and other land categories.

Water-related data, including availability, irrigation, and withdrawals, were obtained from the FAO AQUASTAT database. Socioeconomic indicators, such as population and GDP projections, were gathered from national statistical agencies and the World Bank.

The simplified reference CLEWs diagram for Thailand is shown in below.

Thailand Reference CLEWs Diagram

Key assumptions include: (1) uniform precipitation across land types, (2) energy demand growth linked to GDP growth, (3) fixed irrigation requirements per crop, and (4) technology efficiencies reflecting current Thai power and agricultural systems. Water and energy demand for cooling, irrigation, and pumping are represented via activity ratios, while emissions from diesel and electricity use account for indirect GHG contributions. The model simulates two scenarios for 2037: **achieving 51% renewable electricity generation** as outlined in the PDP and **net zero target in 2050**. These scenarios provide a basis for exploring CO₂eq reduction pathways in Thailand's power sector and assessing the interconnections between energy, water, and land systems.

3. Results

This study presents three main results: (1) the Business-as-Usual (BAU) scenario, (2) a scenario with a 51% shift to renewable energy in Thailand's power generation, and (3) the net-zero emissions target by 2050.

Thailand Electricity Demand

The model projects Thailand's electricity demand to rise steadily in line with GDP growth of 2.5% per year. By 2055, demand nearly doubles from the baseline, highlighting the need for significant capacity expansion. To meet this demand under business-as-usual (BAU), the model optimizes investment toward solar and biomass power plants. However, fossil fuels remain the largest contributors to power generation, with coal and natural gas continuing to play dominant roles.

Thailand Energy Demand (PJ)

Power Plant Production by Technology

In BAU, natural gas remains the primary source of electricity production, followed by coal and biomass. Hydropower contributes a smaller but steady share, while solar and wind expand slightly but do not become major sources without policy intervention. This reliance on fossil fuels locks in high emissions and exposes the system to fuel price risks.

Power Plant Production by Technology (PJ)

Crop Demand

Thailand's crop demand shows a gradual decline over the modelling period, reflecting demographic shifts, including a projected population growth rate of -0.01% . Despite declining demand, agriculture remains a major land user, and trends in food production still affect land allocation.

Land Use Trends

From the baseline to 2055, built-up land shows a consistent upward trend, reflecting urbanization and infrastructure growth. In contrast, cropland steadily decreases, possibly raising concerns about long-term food security and agricultural resilience. Forest land and water bodies remain relatively stable, though land competition between sectors is evident.

Water Demand – Agriculture vs. Irrigation

Water demand analysis indicates that future crop production will increasingly depend on irrigation. The share of irrigated land rises over time, while reliance on rainfed farming decreases. This shift implies greater pressure on surface and groundwater resources, particularly under climate variability.

Scenario 1 – 51% Renewable by 2037

When the model imposes a target of 51% renewable electricity by 2037, fossil fuel use declines. Coal and biomass contributions are reduced, while natural gas, hydro, solar, and wind expand. CO₂ emissions fall by 14.58% compared to BAU, demonstrating the benefits of shifting toward renewables. However, this transition requires a 4.5% increase in investment compared to BAU, underscoring the financial challenge of meeting renewable targets.

Power Plant Production (PJ)

Cost Investment (mUSD)

CO2 Emission (mTon)

Scenario 2 – Net-Zero by 2050

The net-zero scenario requires a dramatic reconfiguration of Thailand's power system. Coal, natural gas, and biomass production fall sharply, while solar, wind, and hydro dominate the energy mix, with wind becoming the largest single source. CO₂ emissions decline rapidly, aligning with the carbon neutrality goal. Importantly, water demand for power generation falls by ~87.8%, a major co-benefit of reducing reliance on water-intensive thermal plants. However, the net-zero pathway requires 158% more investment than BAU, reflecting the high cost of scaling renewables and energy storage.

Power Plan Production (PJ)

Cost Investment (mUSD)

Water Demand For Power Plant Production (BCM)

4. Discussion

The results highlight the central role of renewable energy in Thailand's transition. Meeting the 51% renewable target significantly reduces emissions but demands increased investment and coordinated planning. The net-zero pathway demonstrates even greater environmental benefits, including major reductions in emissions and water demand, but at the cost of a steep rise in investment needs.

These findings underscore the importance of phasing out coal, expanding solar and wind, and investing in energy storage to maintain system reliability. Water savings

in the net-zero scenario point to co-benefits beyond climate mitigation, supporting long-term sustainability. However, the high cost of the net-zero pathway underscores the need for financing strategies, including public–private partnerships and international climate finance.

The model has limitations, as it uses generalized data rather than Thailand-specific inputs. Refining the model with local energy, land, and water datasets, and aligning scenarios with national policies would improve policy relevance. Future research should also consider health co-benefits, such as reduced air pollution from lower fossil fuel use, to strengthen the case for ambitious renewable transitions.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that Thailand’s energy future hinges on its ability to shift from fossil fuels to renewables. The BAU scenario locks in fossil dependence and rising emissions, while the 51% renewable pathway achieves moderate reductions with manageable investment. The net-zero pathway delivers deep decarbonization and significant water savings but requires very large financial commitments.

Key lessons are that Thailand must adopt a phased approach: expand solar, wind, and hydro—targeting an energy mix of approximately 6.7% solar, 89.1% wind, and 1.9% hydro by 2050; accelerate coal phase-out; strengthen water and land-use planning; and secure financing mechanisms. With coordinated policy, investment, and governance, Thailand can align its energy transition with its climate neutrality goals while also enhancing energy security and sustainability.

